

THE ROLE OF THE HERITAGE OF SCIENTISTS OF THE KHORAZM MAMUN ACADEMY IN THE EDUCATION OF THE YOUTH OF THE THIRD RENAISSANCE

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Abstract. The article reveals the role of the scientific heritage of the scientists of the Khorezm Mamun Academy in the education of modern youth. Of great importance in the education of the heirs of the Third Renaissance. At the moment, the rich scientific works recorded by the scientists of Khorezm in the 10th-12th centuries have been studied by world scientists in three areas: the first is scientific research, the second is the publication of texts from sources of that time. in full or partial form, and the third is the works created in Khorezm in the X-XII centuries in the field of exact sciences, this is the translation of sources into different languages of the world.

Keywords: natural sciences, mathematics, astronomy, exact sciences, spiritual heritage, youth education, reading, Third Renaissance.

In the development of the world scientific and philosophical heritage, fundamental research is carried out within the framework of the educational, philosophical, natural science teachings of encyclopedic scientists, in particular their views on the knowledge of the world, nature, the universe and man, the social essence of man [1, p.47]. In particular, the creation of the Universe in the scientific heritage of thinkers who have made a significant contribution to world civilization, exploring the scientific aspects of the doctrine of creation and man, the Universe, nature and social life, revealing the nature of the relationship between man and nature, substantiating the place of natural science views in the development of socio-philosophical thinking is becoming more important today.

In Uzbekistan, special attention is paid to the study of views on the universe and man, nature, social life, spirituality of the individual, education and training in the heritage of ancestors, the use of their ideas in the spirit of the times to educate the younger generation as worthy successors. "Since we have set ourselves the great goal of laying the foundations of the Third Renaissance in our country, we must create an environment and conditions that will educate new Khorezms, Berunites, Ibn Sinas, Ulugbeks, Navoi, Baburs. At the same time, first of all, the development of education and upbringing, the formation of a healthy lifestyle, the promotion of science and innovation should serve as the

main pillars of our national idea” [2]. From this point of view, there is a need for a comprehensive scientific and theoretical study of the scientists of the Mamun Academy of Khorezm, formed on the basis of universal human values, philosophical, natural science views, existential ideas that have a constructive value for human improvement.

Leading world scientific centers and institutions of higher education, including the University of Oxford (England), the University of Hamburg (Germany), the University of Florida (USA), the University of Pennsylvania (USA), the University of Brussels (Belgium), the Queensland University of Technology (Australia), The University of Vienna (Austria), Moscow State University (Russia) and others are conducting fundamental research.

As a result of the study of the natural scientific heritage of the scientists of the Academy of Mamun in the world, a number of the following scientific results were obtained, including: the ideas of Abu Raykhan Beruni about the laws of nature (Oxford University, England) were revealed; Scientific ideas were improved in the works on astronomy, physics and medicine by the scientists of the Mamun Academy (Hamburg University, Germany); Based on the ideas of Abu Ali ibn Sina about necessity, possibility, reality, causal factors and substance (University of Florida, USA); The dialectical nature of the ontological views of Abu Rayhan Beruni (University of Pennsylvania, USA) is revealed; The views of Abu Ali ibn Sina on medicine, Abu Rayhan Beruni's research on geodesy, corpuscular astronomical ideas (University of Brussels, Belgium) are scientifically substantiated; The significance of the scientific views of Muhammad ibn Musa al-Khwarizmi in modern science (Queensland University of Technology, Australia) is revealed; The fundamental ideas and philosophical thoughts of "Kitab ash-Shifa" by Abu Ali ibn Sina (University of Vienna, Austria) were founded; The socio-philosophical and political views of the scientists of the Khorezm Academy of Mamun, views on the factors of development of the socio-economic life of society (Moscow State University, Russia) are revealed.

A number of scientific studies are being carried out in the world to preserve and develop the spiritual heritage, including in the following priority areas: identifying the humanistic significance of the spiritual heritage of the Central Asian encyclopedias in further enriching the history of nature and scientific teachings; creation of scientific concepts related to the formation of feelings of mutual solidarity, compassion, mutual respect; enrichment of the reserves of the national spiritual heritage; to prevent the crisis of social and spiritual and moral identity; problems of dialectical connection between culture and civilization,

peoples and cultures; Substantiating the natural-science, spiritual and philosophical views of the scientists of the Khorezm Academy of Mamun, the influence of discoveries made in the Middle Ages on world science.

The natural science views of the scientists of the Khorezm Mamun Academy were studied by many foreign scientists. In particular, the monographs of orientalist I. Krachkovsky, E. Bertels, V. Bartold, B. Rosenfeld, A. Khalidov became an important source for the study.

Also, monographic studies conducted by such scientists as L. Rode, G. Rudolph, A. Sayili, G. Sarton, F. Sezgin, M. Simon, H. Zuter, J. Wallis, E. Wiedemann on the evolution of the teachings of Central Asian thinkers and is focused on its natural, scientific and philosophical essence, and to a certain extent it is important in revealing such problems as the genesis of socio-philosophical views within the subject.

Various aspects of the heritage of the scientists of the Khorezm Academy of Mamun were studied by scientists from the countries of the Commonwealth of Independent States - B.A. Rosenfeld, H.F. Abdullah-Zade, A.A. Semenov, B.V. Lunin, M.M. Rozhanskaya and others.

Scientists of our country I.M.Mominov, M.M.Khairullaev, A.Akhmedov, P.G.Bulgakov, G.P.Matvievskaia, B.Abdukhalimov, B.R.Karimov, S.Karimova, Kh. .D. Sharipov, T. Usmonov, J. Ibodov, R. Bahadirov, O. Abdullayev and others conducted research on the scientific heritage of Central Asian thinkers, their contribution to world science, scientific activities in Baghdad, "Bayt ul-hikma".

In particular, academician I.M. Muminov describes the essence of the ontological and epistemological views of Ibn Sina, the socio-political views of V. Zohidov and M. Khairullaev [3, 4, p. An-Niot in the works of Donishnom substantiated the importance of his views on mathematics, catastrophes and physics [5, p. 112]. A. Kayumov [6, p. 88] studied the moral views of Ibn Sina, Kh. Gamidov [7, p. 20], R. Nosirov [8, p. 56], natural science, socio-philosophical and moral views. B.R. Karimov [9, p. 52-61] analyzed the concept of emanation in the ontology of Beruni and Ibn Sina. A. Irisov translated the philosophical stories of Ibn Sina [p. 10, 50], S. Ragimov's views on education and training [11, p. 77], A. Imamkhodzhaev [12] and D. Fayzikhodzhaeva [13] who revealed the essence. In the monograph, M. N. Boltaeva explored [14, p. 196] the significance of all aspects of Abu Ali Ibn Sina in the activities of the scientist, especially his thoughts about the harmony of intuition and imagination, intellect and perception in his logical views. O.Abdullayev studied the moral views of Ibn Sina, and M.K.Tulaganova studied the teachings of Abu Nasr Farabi on dialectics, his

scientific legacy of philosophy and logic, ontological and epistemological principles. The influence of Ibn Sina's logical concept of achieving the truth on the formation of a new way of thinking

The author of the doctoral dissertation Masharipova G.K., written on the topic of the influence of the natural-science heritage of the scientists of the Khorezm Academy of Mamun on the development of socio-philosophical thinking and various areas of scientists of the Khorezm Academy of Mamun. In particular, scientific research in the field of natural sciences, exact sciences, mathematics, astronomy, geodesy, mineralogy, medicine and philosophy has been comprehensively studied [15-26].

One of Beruni's contributions to improving the scientific picture of the Universe and the main philosophical problems associated with it is to raise the question of the equality of his teachings on the motion and the motion of the Earth from a geometric point of view. In his work "India", Beruni pays great attention to the theory of the Indian scientist Oryabhata that the Earth moves, and the sky remains in its place without movement, and expresses his critical thoughts on this matter. Also in the correspondence between Beruni and Ibn Sina, various disputes were expressed in the socio-philosophical and natural sciences. According to Beruni, man differs from other creatures in his mind. Beruni tries to rely on material factors and the laws of nature and thinks about the important role of the geographical factor in the life of mankind and society. In his work on India, he analyzes the differences in the traditions of Hindus and Muslims and comes to the conclusion that they also depend on geographical conditions. Beruni expresses the opinion that ".. people were forced to unite in society in order to do something necessary to protect each other, to provide for themselves and others" [15, p.56]. According to him, in addition, a person needs to work honestly.

In conclusion, we can say:

1. Classification of sciences by representatives of the Academy of Mamun, theoretica (النظري) (an-nazari) and practical (العملي) (al-amali), mathematical sciences in "Kitab ash-Shifa" by Abu Ali ibn Sina (علم الهيئة), theory numbers (علم العدد) ('ilm al-'adad), geometry (علم الغيامترية) ('ilm al-handasa), and music (علم الموسيقى) ('ilm al-musiki), al-madhal (المدخل) introduction to logic; al-makulot (المقولات) - categories; al-ibarat (العبارات) - interpretation; al-qiyas (القياس) - syllogism; al-burhan (البرهان) - proof, proof; al-jadal (الجدل) - dispute, dialectic; as-safsata (الفسفة) - sophistry; al-hitaba (الخطابة) - rhetoric; ash-sheer (الشعر) - poetics (the art of poetry); Sharia in the work of Abu Abdullah Khorezmi

"Mafatih al-Ulum" and related sciences of the "Arabs", "non-Arab" sciences (Greeks and other peoples), the original, lower and upper basis in the "Complex of Sciences" of Fakhriddin ar-Razi ", i.e. his contribution to the development of the fields of natural science, mathematics, astronomy, physics, geodesy, his general principles of studying them in theoretical and practical sciences, as well as the features associated with the fact that science and religion are based on Sharia norms and the significant impact of their use on development of socio-philosophical thinking.

2. The concept of a perfect person, knowledge, actions in the works of Abu Rayhan Beruni "Monuments of ancient past generations", "Kitab ash-Shifa", "Donishnama" by Abu Ali ibn Sina, "Complex of Sciences" by Fahriddin al-Razi, "Testament" by Rashiddin Watvot Based on the ideas of entrepreneurship, contentment, enlightenment, raising the morale of young people, strengthening the sense of ownership of reforms and the formation of a healthy worldview, it emphasizes the importance of integration between people. proved on the basis of the hermeneutic method.

3. Dimensions of the Earth's diameter, scientific hypotheses associated with the spherical shape of the Earth in the views of Khorezmian scientists on the structure of the Universe, which prompted the creation of the heliocentric theory, the impact on the development of cosmological teachings in Europe, and the change in ideas about the structure of the universe contributed to the development of natural philosophy, further enriching it ontological and epistemological foundations. It can be recognized that he made an important contribution, recognized by world scientists.

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